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Changes in Accounting and Reporting After Implementation of IFRS 16 “Leases”

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***Annotation:** In the article, the author examines the need to introduce a new generalized standard for accounting and reporting of rental relations. The author outlined the changes in accounting for the landlord and tenant. The article notes that the IFRS 16 standard, in force since 2019, has not changed the accounting of lessors. They continue to report on the lease, dividing it into financial and operating. Tenants have no rental classification since January 2019, and they report all rental obligations.*

***Key words:** Lease, financial lease, operating lease lessee, lessor, rent, lease term.*

In recent years, accounting has undergone significant transformations due to economic processes associated with the development of market relations. The current globalization of the world economy, expressed in the international integration of business and capital, places new increased demands on the quality, timeliness and comparability of information provided to financial markets. The response to these demands was the Accounting Reform Program in accordance with international financial reporting standards.

The process of switching to IFRS is tantamount to investing in the future and, first of all, in better financial reporting. As a result of the transition to a unified financial accounting and reporting standard, there is a reduction in the costs of preparing financial statements, improved means of communication with shareholders and financial markets, and, as one of the positive consequences, lower costs of capital.

However, the movement towards a unified system of standards is associated with serious changes: accounting is constantly becoming more complex, covers more and more new observation objects, uses new techniques and methods, and improves its technical support. In addition, immediately after the start of the implementation of the accounting reform program in accordance with IFRS, specialists began to face a number of problems.

Since 2019, enterprises and organizations using leases and reporting under IFRS have been using IFRS 16 to replace the previous version of IAS 17. The new changes did not affect the accounting of lessors, but had a significant impact on the accounting of tenants. Lease disclosures have increased. Accountants are forced to delve deeper into accounting methods and carefully analyze the correctness of long-term leases being reflected in the report.

What changes have occurred in reporting after the implementation of the latest version of the IFRS 16 "Lease" standard. This standard forced tenant companies to show previously silent assets in their reporting: for them, the differentiation of leases by type has lost its relevance. Now business recognizes any leased objects as assets. The simplified scheme retained its significance for contracts lasting less than a year and transactions with low-value objects.

There were no changes in the accounting and reporting of lessors after the adoption of the new standard. They continue to classify leases into one of two groups: financial - assets are removed from the lessor's balance sheet; operating - assets remain on the lessor's balance sheet.

In most cases, an entity recognizes a finance lease if it expects to sell the asset to the lessee at the end of the lease. That is, the parties use rent instead of lending, without resorting to the services of a guarantor and posting collateral.

1. upon expiration of the lease term, the asset becomes the property of the lessee; upon expiration of the lease term, the lessor expects the lessee to purchase the asset at a reduced price;
2. the service life of the object is comparable to the term of the lease agreement; the amount of the initial rental payment is comparable to the price of the property; The specifics of the leased property allow it to be used exclusively by the tenant.

In other cases, when, when handing over an asset, the agreement does not contain the characteristic features of a financial lease, the lessor recognizes an operating lease. Companies classified most transactions as operating leases while operating under the old IFRS 17. This gave the right not to include leased assets in the reports and reduce the value of assets in the documents.

Under IFRS 16, the division of leases remains relevant only for lessors. According to the rules of operating lease, after the completion of the contract, the lessor cannot: obtain property rights to the object; buy an object at a reduced price.

Today, tenants are required to acknowledge most leases. After the conclusion of the contract, lease obligations and rights to use assets are taken into account in the balance sheet of the companies. On the income statement, the accountant reports depreciation expense and interest accrued on the balance of the lease liability.

For the lessor, entering into a finance lease means adding receivables from the investment to the balance sheet.

In the case of a finance lease, the lessor recognizes receivables from the financial investment in the balance sheet.

In accounting for finance leases under IFRS 16, the accountant reflects the transfer of the object and its write-off from the balance sheet. In the case of an operating lease, the accountant enters the income on a company's income statement on a straight - line basis over the entire duration of the lease. No interest is charged on such rentals.

Initial recognition of the right to use the asset; lease payment obligations accounts receivable continue to recognize the asset Subsequent valuation and accounting right-of-use expenses for: depreciation of the asset; interest on the balance of the obligation; income on accounts receivable; A decrease in accounts receivable by the amount of lease payments received recognizes income on a straight-line basis over the entire lease term.

New amendments to this standard became effective on January 1, 2024, affecting lease liabilities in a sale and leaseback, and adding requirements to explain how an entity will account for sales and leasebacks after the transaction date. The amendments will affect how a seller-lessee will be required to account for transactions and variable lease payments arising in a sale-leaseback transaction.

Such payments will now need to be included in the lease liability. Under the new amendment, when subsequently measuring lease liabilities to a sale transaction, “lease payments” or “restated lease payments” will need to be defined so that the seller-lessee does not recognize gains and losses on its remaining occupancy rights.

The seller-lessee will value the right-of-use asset at present value. And the lease liability will be measured as the present value of expected lease payments. That is, it will have to reduce the lease liability as if the “lease payments” calculated at the date of the transaction had been paid.

Any difference arising between these lease payments and the amounts actually paid will be recognized in profit or loss. The seller-lessee will be able to determine the lease payments that are deductible from the lease liability in several ways: as “expected lease payments” or as “equal periodic payments” over the lease term.

The amendments are effective for annual periods beginning on or after 1 January 2024, but early application is permitted. Changes must be made retrospectively in accordance with IAS Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors for sale and leaseback transactions occurring after the date of first application.

Conclusions The IFRS 16 standard, in force since 2019, has not changed the accounting of lessors. They continue to report on the lease, dividing it into financial and operating. Tenants have no rental classification since January 2019, and they report all rental obligations. This led to an increase in assets and liabilities in companies' financial statements, as well as an increase in depreciation and interest expenses

However, this did not have such a dramatic effect on profit accounting due to the disappearance of the operating lease item. Under the new amendment to IFRS 16 Leases, Lease Liabilities in Sale and Leasebacks, effective 1 January 2024, seller-lessees will be required to remeasure or restate sale and leaseback transactions entered into since 2019 year.

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